

Sustainability Concepts in the Design of High-Rise Buildings: The Case of Diagrid Systems

Giulia Milana, Konstantinos Gkoumas* and Franco Bontempi

giuliamilana@live.it, konstantinos.gkoumas@uniroma1.it, franco.bontempi@uniroma1.it
Department of Structural and Geotechnical Engineering, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Abstract: One of the evocative structural design solutions for sustainable tall buildings is embraced by the diagrid (diagonal grid) structural scheme. Diagrid, with a perimeter structural configuration characterized by a narrow grid of diagonal members involved both in gravity and in lateral load resistance, has emerged as a new design trend for tall-shaped complex structures, and is becoming increasingly popular due to aesthetics and structural performance. Since it requires less structural steel than a conventional steel frame, it provides for a more sustainable structure. This study focuses on the structural performance of a steel tall building, using FEM nonlinear analyses. Numerical comparisons between a traditional outrigger system and different diagrid configurations (with three different diagrid inclinations) are presented for a building of 40 stories, with a total height of 160m, and a footprint of 36m x 36m. The sustainability of the building (in terms of structural steel weight saving) is assessed, together with the structural behavior.

Keywords: Diagrid Structures, Tall Buildings, FEM, Sustainability, Design Criteria.

Introduction

Tall building structural design developed rapidly in the last decades, focusing among else on the sustainability improvement. In fact, sustainability in the urban and built environment is a key issue for the wellbeing of people and society, and sustainable development is nowadays a first concern both for public authorities and for private investors. One of the evocative structural design solutions for sustainable tall buildings is embraced by the diagrid (diagonal grid) structural scheme.

This study focuses on the Sustainability of Structural Systems, within two specific topics:

- The use of steel in high-rise buildings;
- The conception and design of sustainable diagrid high-rise buildings.

The inspiration for this study arises from the impact that the construction industry has on the environment, in terms of use of resources and production of waste, and the social need that calls for investigating sustainable solutions.

Sustainability in the Urban Environment

Sustainability is a difficult and complex issue, and an elusive one. It is enormously important since it has to do with the chances of humankind surviving on this planet. At the rate that the human race is using scarce and limited resources it appears that, unless measures are taken now - and if there is still time - the future of civilization, at least as we understand it now, is uncertain. It leads to a better life for the present generation and survival for generations to come,

enhancing their ability to cope with the world that they will inherit. Per current level of understanding, sustainability covers the following elements (Adams 2006):

- Economic benefit;
- Resource efficiency;
- Environmental protection; and,
- Social development.

A process that is designed for only economic and environmental concerns is classified as viable; a process that is designed for only environmental and social concerns is classified as bearable; and a process that is designed for economic and social concerns is equitable. Thus, a sustainable process in one that covers all three dimensions (figure 1).

Figure 1. Triple Bottom Line of Sustainability - Adapted from Adams (2006)

Sustainability in the urban environment is a key issue for the wellbeing of people and society.

Sustainable development, defined as the “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (UN 1987) is nowadays a first concern for public authorities and the private sector, and is shaped by incentives and sanctions. Although sustainability goals are not uniquely identified, a total plan for sustainability requires, in a cost efficiency balance (ISE 1999):

- Reduction of emission of greenhouse gases;
- More efficient use (and reuse) of resources;
- Minimization and constructive reuse of waste;
- Reduction of harmful effects from construction activities and building occupation.

The above goals find their application in the construction and built environment sector.

Sustainability in the Construction and Built Environment Sector

In the recent years, the construction sector is more and more oriented towards the promotion of sustainability in all its activities. The goal to achieve is the optimization of performances, over the whole life cycle, with respect to environmental, economic and social requirements. According to the latest advances, the concept of sustainability applied to constructions covers a number of braches such as life-cycle costing, ecology durability and even structural design. Several procedures and design tools are proposed in different international frameworks. Indeed, the current trend in civil engineering is moving towards lifetime engineering, with the aim to implement integrated methodologies that consider as a whole all the sustainability requirements according to time-dependent multi performance-based design approaches (Sarja *et al.* 2005).

The design, construction and operation of “green” buildings is nowadays regulated by international guidelines, codes and standards (see for example the green building evaluation and certification system USGBC, 2009). What emerges is a variety of widely acknowledged and recognizable standards, especially for what regards ranking and certification systems (Nguyen and Altan 2011). In fact, the entire concepts of “sustainable development” and “sustainable building” are clumsily defined, with different and sometimes contrasting definitions. Berardi (2013) discusses in detail several aspects of sustainable development (namely its time dependency, its multi-space and multi-scale levels, its multiple dimensions and its social dependencies) and arrives at a definition of what is a sustainable building by means of a number of principles.

It is important to add that even though sustainability has mostly a social character, benefits of sustainable design are not only to the general public but also for the building stakeholders,

including owners, who benefit from the increased value of the property.

Sustainable design leads to innovation since it demands inventive solutions, and eventually is supported by a cultural shift, evident from national level reviews and surveys (Robin and Poon 2009; Tae and Shin 2009).

Sustainability issues are wide-ranging, but the main focus in the building industry is the reduction of energy consumption in construction and use. Although the trend is to arrive to a so-called Net Zero Energy Buildings, for which a balance between energy flow and renewable supply options is established, the path to this goal is still very long (Srinivasan *et al.* 2011). Ramesh *et al.* (2010) provide a breakdown of energy use in the various phases of building lifecycle (manufacture, use and demolition), and highlight the higher contribution of the operating phase, and the variability of the results for different climates, different building uses etc. This is especially important for structural parts and systems, where recycling, reusing and material minimization can be important aspects (Vezzoli and Manzini 2008). The possibility to implement active systems for the energy efficiency of buildings is also an alternative, providing energy by sustainable resources (see for example Gkoumas *et al.* 2013).

The role of steel structures towards sustainable development has been also recognized, due to several advantages such as the offsite prefabrication and the consequent reduction of site waste and impacts, the easy dismantling process, the high recycling rates of the material and components, etc. (figure 2). Nowadays, the steel construction industry has been giving more attention to the questions related to life-cycle costing, ecology, durability and sustainability of steel products and components (Landolfo *et al.* 2011).

Figure 2. Environmental Advantages of Steel Construction –Adapted from <http://arcelormittal.com>

When evaluating the sustainability of a building, the life cycle approach is required, taking into account all phases of a building's life, including material production, transportation to the construction site, construction, operation, demolition or deconstruction, and end of life.

Sustainability and Tall Buildings

The number of tall buildings designed and built is increasingly always more rapidly. They are evolving in height, construction materials, use and compartmental composition. The driving forces behind this progression are inevitably financial, political and environmental, but it is modern technological developments, both structural and material, which have truly enabled the continued evolution of these buildings. The tall building of today is a completely different entity to that of a decade ago, with the propensity for change even greater in the immediate future. Advancements in structural engineering have arisen to make possible the increase in height, size and complexity, the reduction of cost and carbon footprint as well as architectural imagination and economic versatility of these buildings (Cowlard *et al.* 2013).

Two of the most important design requirements for any building structural design are strength and stiffness, while for very tall buildings with a high height-to-width aspect ratio, stiffness constraints generally govern the design. The structural systems with diagonals, such as braced tubes and diagrids, are generally very stiff and, in turn, very effective in resisting lateral loads among various structural systems developed for tall buildings.

Two modes of deformation, bending and shear deformation, contribute primarily to the total deformation. In general, as a building becomes taller and its height-to-width aspect ratio becomes higher, the contribution of the bending deformation becomes more important. Technically, there are infinite numbers of bending and shear deformation combinations that can meet the design parameter. This also means that there are numerous design scenarios possible to meet the stiffness requirements (Moon 2008).

Historical Perspective

In the late nineteenth century, early tall building developments were based on economic equations - increasing rentable area by stacking office spaces vertically and maximizing the rents of these offices by introducing as much natural light as possible.

In terms of structural systems, most tall buildings in the early twentieth century employed steel rigid frames with wind bracing. Their enormous heights at that time were achieved not through notable technological evolution, but through

excessive use of structural materials (for example the Empire State Building of the early 1930s). Due to the absence of advanced structural analysis techniques, they were quite over-designed. The mid-twentieth century, after the war, was the era of mass production based on the International Style defined already before the war, and the previously developed technology.

Structural systems for tall buildings have undergone dramatic changes since the demise of the conventional rigid frames in the 1960s as the predominant type of structural system for steel or concrete tall buildings. With the emergence of the tubular forms still conforming to the International Style, such changes in the structural form and organization of tall buildings were necessitated by the emerging architectural trends in design in conjunction with the economic demands and technological developments in the realms of rational structural analysis and design made possible by the advent of high-speed digital computers. Beginning in the 1980s, the once-prevalent Miesian tall buildings were then largely replaced by the façade characteristics of postmodern, historical, diagrid and deconstructivist expressions. This was not undesirable because the new generation of tall buildings broke the monotony of the exterior tower form and gave rise to novel high-rise expressions. Innovative structural systems involving tubes, mega frames, core-and-outrigger systems, artificially damped structures, and mixed steel-concrete systems are some of the new developments since the 1960s.

The primary structural skeleton of a tall building can be visualized as a vertical cantilever beam with its base fixed in the ground. The structure has to carry both the vertical gravity loads and the lateral wind and earthquake loads. The gravity loads are principally the dead and live loads, while lateral loads tend to snap the building or topple it. The building must therefore have an adequate shear and bending resistance and must not lose its vertical load-bearing capacity.

The quantity of materials required for resisting lateral loads, on the other hand, is even higher and could well exceed other structural costs if a rigid-frame system is used for very tall structures. This calls for a structural system that goes well beyond the simple rigid frame concept. Khan (1973) argued that the rigid frame that had dominated tall building design and construction so long was not the only system fitting for tall buildings. Because of a better understanding of the mechanics of material and member behavior, he reasoned that the structure could be viewed in a holistic manner, that is, the building could be analyzed in three dimensions, supported by computer simulations, rather than as a series of planar systems in each principal direction. Feasible structural systems, according to him, are

rigid frames, shear walls, interactive frame-shear wall combinations, belt trusses, and the various other tubular systems.

Structural systems of tall buildings can be divided into two broad categories: interior structures and exterior structures (figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3. Interior structures (from Ali and Moon 2007)

Figure 4. Exterior structures (from Ali and Moon 2007)

This classification is based on the distribution of the components of the primary lateral load-resisting system over the building. A system can be referred to as an interior structure when the major part of the lateral load resisting system is located within the interior of the building. Likewise, if the major part of the lateral load-resisting system is located at the building perimeter, a system can be referred to as an exterior structure. It should be noted, however, that any interior structure is likely to have some minor components of the lateral load-resisting system at the building perimeter, and any exterior structure may have some minor components within the interior of the building (Ali and Moon 2007).

In plain words, steel-framed buildings with a rigid frame can be economical for medium rise buildings up to 20 stories. A vertical steel shear truss at the central core of the building can be economical for buildings up to 40 stories. Finally, a combination

of central vertical shear trusses with horizontal outrigger trusses is most suited for up to 60-stories, this being the most common form of tall building structure in the US for example. For even taller buildings, it becomes essential to transfer all gravity loads to the exterior frame to avoid overturning effects. Rigid framed tubes, braced tubes and bundled tube structures have been developed to reach up to over 100. There are many ways to construct tall buildings and in practice it is the desired use of a building, which predominantly determines its design. The exterior shape and the materials of the façade have the greatest impact on the outside public, whilst the arrangement of spaces inside determines the efficiency of a building's use by its occupants. The choice of materials for the structural frame is determined primarily to satisfy those requirements, with comparisons made of the most economical form that will do the job (Pank *et al.* 2002).

Diagrid Structures

Diagrid is a perimeter structural configuration characterized by a narrow grid of diagonal members that are involved both in gravity and in lateral load resistance. Since it requires less structural steel than a conventional steel frame, it provides for a more sustainable structure

The diagrid system is not a new invention. In fact, an early example of today's diagrid-like structure is the 13-story IBM Building in Pittsburg of 1963. However, the implementation in a larger scale of such tall building was not practical due to high cost related to the difficult node connections. It is only in recent years that technology allowed a more reasonable cost of diagrid node connections (Leonard 2004).

With specific reference to tall buildings, diagrids are increasingly employed due to their structural efficiency as well as architectural suggestion. In fact, diagrid structures can be seen as the latest mutation of tube structures, which, starting from the frame tube configuration, have increased structural efficiency thanks to the introduction of exterior mega-diagonals in the braced tube solution.

The perimeter configuration still holds the maximum bending resistance and rigidity, while, with respect to the braced tube, the mega-diagonal members are diffusely spread over the façade, giving rise to closely spaced diagonal elements and allowing for the complete elimination of the conventional vertical columns.

The difference between conventional exterior-braced frame structures and current diagrid structures is that, for diagrid structures, almost all the conventional vertical columns are eliminated. This is possible because the diagonal members in diagrid structural systems can carry gravity loads as well as lateral forces due to their triangulated configuration

in a distributive and uniform manner. Compared with conventional framed tubular structures without diagonals, diagrid structures are much more effective in minimizing shear deformation because they carry shear by axial action of the diagonal members, while conventional tubular structures carry shear by the bending of the vertical columns and horizontal spandrels (Ali and Moon 2007).

Diagrid Module

A diagrid structure is modeled as a vertical cantilever beam on the ground, and subdivided longitudinally into modules according to the repetitive diagrid pattern. Each module is defined by a single level of diagrids that extend over multiple stories.

Being the diagrid a triangulated configuration of structural members, the geometry of the single module plays a major role in the internal axial force distribution, as well as in conferring global shear and bending rigidity to the building structure.

The analysis of the diagrid structures can be carried out in a preliminary stage by dividing the building elevation into groups of stacking floors, with each group corresponding to a diagrid module (Moon 2011).

As shown in the studies by Moon *et al.* 2007 and Moon, 2008, the diagrid module under gravity loads G is subjected to a downward vertical force, $N_{G,mod}$, causing the two diagonals being both in compression and the horizontal chord in tension (figure 5a).

Figure 5. Diagrid Module: (a) Effect of Gravity Load, (b) Effect of Overturning Moment and (c) Effect of Shear Force –from (Mele *et al.* 2014)

Under a horizontal load W , the overturning moment M_W causes vertical forces in the apex joint of the diagrid modules $N_{W,mod}$. The direction and intensity of this force depends on the position of the

diagrid module, with upward/downward direction and maximum intensity for the modules located on the windward/leeward façades, respectively, and gradually decreasing values for the modules located on the web sides (figure 5b). The global shear V_W causes a horizontal force in the apex joint of the diagrid modules, $V_{W,mod}$, which intensity depends on the position of the module with respect to the direction of wind load, since the shear force V_W is mainly absorbed by the modules located on the web façades, i.e. parallel to the load direction (figure 5c).

In the formulations provided in figure 5, for deriving internal forces in the diagrid elements, it has been implicitly assumed that the external loads is transferred to the diagrid module only at the apex node of the module itself (Mele *et al.* 2014).

Geometry and Design Criteria

Diagrid structures, like all the tubular configurations, utilize the overall building plan dimension for counteracting overturning moment and providing flexural rigidity. However, this potential bending efficiency of tubular configurations is never fully achievable due to shear deformations that arise in the building ‘webs’; with this regard, diagrid systems, which provide shear resistance and rigidity by means of axial action in the diagonal members, rather than bending moment in beams and columns, allows for a nearly full exploitation of the theoretical bending resistance. This is the main reason underlying the extraordinary efficiency of diagrid systems.

Being the diagrid a triangulated configuration of structural members, the geometry of the single module plays a major role in the internal axial force distribution, as well as in conferring global shear and bending rigidity to the building structure. As shown in the study by Moon *et al.* (2007), while a module angle equal to 35° ensures the maximum shear rigidity to the diagrid system, the maximum engagement of diagonal members for bending stiffness would correspond to an angle value of 90° , i.e. vertical columns. Thus, in diagrid systems, where vertical columns are completely eliminated and both shear and bending stiffness must be provided by diagonals, a balance between these two conflicting requirements should be searched for defining the optimal angle of the diagrid module (Mele *et al.* 2014).

Structural Analysis

The considered structure is a 40-story building, for a total height of 160m, and a footprint of about 36m x 36m. Its function is for not-public offices. The building is located in Latina (Lazio, Italy). Regarding local wind and earthquake loading conditions, the area where the building is placed is characterized by a class of roughness ‘‘B’’ (urban and sub-urban areas)

and a class of exposition to wind “IV”; the seismic zone corresponds II seismic level (PGA 0,15-0,25).

During the conceptual design, two different structural design solutions were proposed: outrigger and diagrid. Consequently, comparisons are performed to select the most efficient structural system and to reduce the material used. Objective of the study is to verify advantages and disadvantages, both in direct economic terms (limited to the amount of structural steel) and in structural performance. Figure 6 outlines the different structural configurations.

Figure 6. Structural Models (a- Outrigger Structure; b- Diagrid Structure $\alpha=42^\circ$; c- Diagrid Structure $\alpha=60^\circ$; d- Diagrid Structure $\alpha=75^\circ$)

Outrigger Structure

The building plant is symmetric with respect to the X axis; it has an octagonal footprint, approximated by a square of 35m x 35 m. The overall height of the structure is 160 m, while the distance between two consecutive floors is 4 m. The structure (and the model) have been realized in order to make a diagonal bracings system resists horizontal actions of the wind. The diagonal elements of the system consist in St. Andrew cross-bracings.

In order to reduce the building deformability, a rigid plane is introduced. This plane is called outrigger; this reinforcement, located at the 29th floor (between 112m and 116m), is realized by introducing braces expanded vertically for all façades in exam. These outriggers are located on two facades in direction X and on two cross-sections in direction Y at $X=4\text{m}$ and $X=31\text{m}$.

Diagrid Structures

The plant of the buildings is symmetric with respect to both the X and the Y axis, and it has a square footprint of 36mx36m. The overall height of the structure is 160 m, while the distance between two consecutive floors is 4 m.

Some generic considerations are necessary. Typically, a diagrid structure is subdivided longitudinally into modules according to the repeated diagrid pattern. Each module is defined by a single level of diagrid that extends over multiple stories. In the building here presented, there are 4-story modules. The structural efficiency of diagrid for tall buildings can be maximized by configuring them to have optimum grid geometries.

The optimal angle of diagonals is highly dependent upon the building height. Since the optimal angle of the columns for maximum bending rigidity is 90 degrees and that of the diagonals for maximum shear rigidity is about 35 degrees, it is expected that the optimal angle of diagonal members for diagrid structures will fall between these angles. This study introduces three intermediate angles: 42, 60 and 75 degrees respectively.

Numerical Modelling and Results

The three diagrid buildings have two structural systems working in parallel: the first is internal and it is made of a rigid frame system which only reacts to gravity loads, while the second is perimetral and it is made of a diagonal grid system which reacts both to vertical and horizontal loads.

The internal structure, as any other ordinary frame structure, is composed by columns and main and secondary beams, while, the external one is composed by diagonal and horizontal elements (without columns).

All the components of the internal system are placed at a distance of 6m in plant, thus creating square footprints of 6mx6m. The internal columns transmit vertical loads to the ground, while the perimetral ones do not; in fact their function is to link the generic diagrid module to the floors included in it. In more details, the external columns receive the loads from the perimetral beams and they transfer these loads to the horizontal elements of the module. The extension of the external columns is four-story length as the diagrid module. Passing from one module to the consecutive one, the perimetral beams are replaced by the horizontal diagrids. In this way, the two structures “communicate” every four floors.

All of the vertical elements are tapered every four stories, since the size of each diagrid module changes. While Italian profiles are used for interior structure, American ones are used for the perimetral structure.

The computational code SAP2000 (version 16.0.0) has been used for all analysis. The structural model takes into count the real distribution of the masses, while the effect of non-structural elements on the global stiffness has not been considered. Figure 7 provides an overview of the deflected diagrid configurations.

Figure 7. Different Diagrid FEM Models

Weight and Structural Periods

In this research the weight saving is the most important issue, since this is considered as the most important sustainable aspect. For all diagrid buildings an important weight saving occurs, therefore, in all cases the diagrid system results better than the ordinary outrigger for what regards sustainability.

The weight of the structures is calculated without considering the floors. This is due to the fact that all the structures have the same number of floors.

In table 1 and figure 8 the comparison among the structures is presented. The percentage of savings is calculated compared to the weight of the outrigger structure.

Table 1. Weight and Weight Saving

Structure	Weight (ton)	Weight-Saving (%)
Outrigger	8052	-
Diagrid 42°	6523	19
Diagrid 60°	5931	26
Diagrid 75°	5389	33

Figure 8. Comparison of Weights

Verifications

It is important to verify the structural configurations for both Serviceability Limit States (SLS) and Ultimate Limit States (ULS). To this aim, displacements are confronted with thresholds provided in codes and standards, and pushover analyses are performed.

SLS: Horizontal Displacements

For the verification of the service limit states, the absolute horizontal displacements are considered. The points of control used are placed every four stories (16m). Figure 9 presents these displacements, together with the threshold values provided by the Italian Building Code (NTC 2008). It is easy to see that all structures are verified by a great margin.

Figure 9. Comparison of Horizontal Displacements

ULS: Pushover Analyses

In order to evaluate the ductility of the structures, a non-linear static (Push-Over) analysis is conducted. A lamped plasticity model has been implemented taking into account the material non-linearity. For simulating this non-linearity, plastic hinges are used. The Pushover analysis is conducted on the 3D model for all structures with the same static loads and hinges, in order to have a direct comparison of the results.

The horizontal (wind) load applied to the structure is a triangular load, increasing with height.

The concentrated forces, are applied to the geometric centers of each floor and represent the equivalent static forces normalized.

To simulate the non-linearity of material, plastic hinges are introduced. Two different kinds of hinges are considered: axial hinges, used for all elements of the outrigger structures and the perimetral system in the diagrid structures, and, bending hinges for the internal columns in the diagrid structures.

In addition, and in order to consider the effect of geometric non-linearity in the structural behavior, another kind of non-linear static analysis is introduced: P-Delta analysis. The P-Delta effect refers specifically to the non-linear geometric effect of a large tensile or compressive, direct stress upon transverse bending and shear behavior.

In order to take into account the effect of gravity loads upon the lateral stiffness of building structures, a non-linear case is created considering only permanent vertical loads 'VertNonLin'. Another load case, 'DeadNonLin', is also considered, in which only the dead loads of the structure are accounted for.

Figures 10-12 report the comparison of the capacity curves of all structures. In order to simplify the reading of results all graphs are presented with the same scale axis. The curves are divided according to the different types of analysis: with or without P-Delta effects; in the P-Delta cases, two load-cases are considered.

Figure 10. Comparison of 'Pushover' Curves

Figure 11. Comparison of 'Pushover+Dead' Curves

Figure 12. Comparison of 'Pushover+Vert' Curves

Comparison and Choice of the Best Model

Based on the capacity curves of the previous paragraph, it is possible to obtain three of the four values from which we can identify the model with the best behavior.

These properties are:

- Strength (R)
- Stiffness (K)
- Ductility (μ)

For the analyses, the same considerations made in the previous section remain valid.

In the chart of figure 13 the features for calculating these properties are identified. The capacity curve in the figure is an example of the realization of the features.

Figure 13. Definition of the Main Features

The features represented in the chart are:

- D_y : yield displacement
- D_u : maximum displacement
- F_y : yield force
- F_{max} : maximum force

From these features, it is possible to obtain the mechanical properties of interest in the following way:

$$R = F_{max} : \text{Strength}$$

$$K = \frac{F_y}{D_y} : \text{Stiffness}$$

$$\mu = \frac{D_u}{D_y} : \text{Ductility}$$

Using these properties as well as the weight of the structure, the buildings are compared and the best structure is chosen through an equation defined in the following paragraph.

All these features are calculated just for the 'Pushover+Vert' curve, because it is the most realistic case.

Definition of a Performance Equation

An equation that helps to identify the structure with the best behavior is defined below. All terms of this equation are normalized to the features of the outrigger structure, that is, the reference building. These terms are multiplied with amplification coefficients. For the weight, a coefficient equal to 1.2 is considered, while for the other terms the coefficients are equal to 1. In fact, weight is very important for the sustainable aspect. The higher the outcome, the better the behavior of the structure.

$$Eq.: \frac{R}{R_0} + \frac{K}{K_0} + \frac{\mu}{\mu_0} + 1,2 \left[\frac{(P - P_0)}{P_0} + 1 \right]$$

In the above equation, the subscript “0” identifies the features relative to the outrigger structure. Given that the behavior improves for a reduced weight a higher expression is used.

In table 2 the results of this equation are provided for each structure.

Table 2. Weight and Weight Saving

	OUTRIGGER	DIAGRID 42°	DIAGRID 60°	DIAGRID 75°
	P+V	P+V	P+V	P+V
R (kN)	94775	110185	104972	97131
K (kN/m)	77143	80615	71306	60897
μ	1,535	3,587	5,681	2,564
P (kg)	8052	6523	5931	5389
Eq.	4,20	5,06	5,52	4,67

In order to have a clearer view, is possible to represent the terms of the equation, multiplied for the relative coefficients, on the axes of a radar chart.

In figure 14, the chart is reported in accordance to the performed analyses.

Figure 14. Comparison of Models for the ‘Pushover+Vert’ Case

From the results of the equation and the examination of the chart, it is possible to observe that the model with the best behavior is the diagrid

structure with diagonal members having an inclination of 60°.

Thus, the diagrid structure with an intermediate inclination results as the best model; in fact this structure leads to an important saving of weight while at the same time, offers a high performance in terms of strength, stiffness and ductility.

Conclusions

In this study, the Sustainability of a complex structural system has been inquired, focusing on two specific topics:

- The use of steel, an intrinsically sustainable material, especially for high-rise buildings;
- the conception and design of sustainable diagrid high-rise buildings.

The inspiration for this study arises from the impact that the construction industry has on the environment, in terms of use of resources and production of waste, and the social need that calls for investigating sustainable solutions.

Among the finding, it has been shown and quantified the way in which diagrid structures lead to a considerable saving of (steel) material compared to more traditional structural schemes such as outrigger structures. Furthermore, the performance of diagrid structures has been assessed, not only in terms of material reduction, but also in terms of safety, serviceability and structural robustness.

In particular, different diagrid structures were considered, namely, three geometric configurations, with inclination of diagonal members of 42°, 60° and 75°. These configurations, in addition to allowing a considerable saving of weight, guarantee a better performance in terms of strength, stiffness and ductility.

Among the diagrid structures considered the one with the best overall behavior results to be the one with 60° diagonal element inclination.

Of course, there are limitations to this study. Additional loading scenarios should be accounted for, in order to have a broader insight on the structural behavior. In addition, the defined performance equation is calibrated with specific coefficient values that highlight the sustainability aspect.

Nevertheless, the initial results provide a starting point, and together with the proposed methodology, contribute obtaining a preliminary assessment of the sustainability of diagrid structures.

Acknowledgements

This study presents results from the Master in Science Thesis successfully defended from one of the authors (Giulia Milana), to the Department of Structural and Geotechnical Engineering of the Sapienza University of Rome, with the other authors co-advising. The www.francobontempi.org research

group from Sapienza University of Rome is also gratefully acknowledged. Finally, the study was partially supported by the research spin-off StroNGER s.r.l. (www.stronger2012.com) from the fund "FILAS - POR FESR LAZIO 2007/2013 - Support for the research spin-off".

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